

The Kinetics of Slow Coagulation. Part II.

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Numerous attempts have been made from time to time to experimentally verify Smoluchowski's theory. Thus Westgren and Reitstötter (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1918, 92, 750), working with coarse gold sol and Kruyt and van Arkel (*Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1920, 39, 654), in the case of selenium sols have shown that Smoluchowski's theory is capable of experimental verification in the region of rapid coagulation of colloids. When, however, attempts were made to verify Smoluchowski's theory with respect to slow coagulation, the agreement with experimental data was not satisfactory. Thus Kruyt and van Arkel (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 32, 29), Mukherjee and Papaconstantinou (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1563), Mukherjee and Mazumdar (*ibid.*, 1924, 125, 785), Dessai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 24, 181), Mehta and Miss Joseph (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 182), working with different sols have all found more or less marked divergences from the theory.

Smoluchowski has accounted for the difference between slow and rapid coagulation by introducing a factor ϵ in his equation for rapid

coagulation,
$$V_1 = \frac{V_0}{1 + \epsilon \frac{t}{T}}$$
,

where ϵ is unity in the case of rapid coagulation and has a value less than unity in the case of slow coagulation. This would mean that in the case of rapid coagulation all the collisions between completely discharged particles end in adherence, while in the case of slow coagulation only a fraction of them are so, owing to the residual charges possessed by the particles. He further assumes that in the latter case the fraction ϵ remains a constant during the course of each coagulation, which demands that all the different coagulation curves should be "affine" to one another. But an examination of the series of coagulation curves shows that this is far from the case. This fact together with the general autocatalytic nature of these curves which cannot find a place

in Smoluchowski's theory, goes definitely to show that the rates of slow coagulation are being influenced by some additional factor, which vanishes when the particles are completely discharged.

Now of the two factors, (i) the probability of collision and, (ii) the probability of adherence, which determine coagulation, it is only the latter that is affected by the residual charge of the partially discharged particles (*cf.* Kruyt, A. Smith, "Colloid Chemistry" Vol. I, p. 307). It was hoped, therefore, that a consideration of the electrical energy possessed by the particles as they grow, might throw some light on the behaviour of the adherence factor during slow coagulation.

It has been shown by Burton (*Phil. Mag.*, 1906, 12, 472), that a colloid particle with its double layer can be considered as a charged condenser, having an energy E , given by the equation $E = Q^2/2C$, where Q is the charge and C is the capacity of the condenser. Further, if we assume (*cf.* Smoluchowski) P_2, P_3, P_4 , the double, triple and quadruple particles formed from the single particles P_1 as spherical, then their radii r_2, r_3, r_4 , etc., and capacities C_2, C_3, C_4 , etc., can easily be expressed in terms of r_1 and C_1 , the radius and capacity of the primary particle. Thus,

$$r_2 = r_1 \sqrt[3]{2} = 1.26 r_1$$

$$r_3 = 1.44 r_1$$

$$r_4 = 1.59 r_1$$

$$r_5 = 1.71 r_1$$

Similarly the capacities (assuming d , the thickness of the double layer for the primary particles to be the same as for the multiple particles) are as follows:

$$C_1 = \frac{r_1^2}{d}$$

$$C_2 = \frac{r_2^2}{d} = \frac{(1.26r_1)^2}{d} = 1.59C_1$$

$$C_3 = \frac{r_3^2}{d} = 2.07C_1$$

$$C_4 = \frac{r_4^2}{d} = 2.59C_1$$

$$C_5 = \frac{r_5^2}{d} = 2.92C_1.$$

Now, if two charged condensers are joined together it can be proved that there is always a loss of electrical energy except when the initial potentials are the same. Thus, if Q_1 , C_1 and V_1 , and Q_2 , C_2 , and V_2 be the charges, capacities and potentials of two charged condensers, then the total energy before connecting is given by the equation,

$$E_1 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{Q_1^2}{C_1} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{Q_2^2}{C_2}.$$

After connecting we have,

$$E_2 = \frac{(Q_1 + Q_2)^2}{2(C_1 + C_2)}$$

whence the loss of energy,

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 - E_2 &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{Q_1^2}{C_1} + \frac{Q_2^2}{C_2} - \frac{(Q_1 + Q_2)^2}{(C_1 + C_2)} \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{(Q_1 C_2 - Q_2 C_1)^2}{C_1 C_2 (C_1 + C_2)}. \end{aligned}$$

This is equal to zero, only when $Q_1 C_2 = Q_2 C_1$

or when $\frac{Q_1}{C_1} = \frac{Q_2}{C_2}$, i.e., when $V_1 = V_2$.

If then we assume that the charges q_2, q_3, q_4 , etc. of particles P_2, P_3, P_4 , etc., are equal to $2q_1, 3q_1, 4q_1$, etc., respectively, q_1 being the charge of the primary P_1 , it will be possible to compute the energy losses from equation (1) for the different cases corresponding to combination between differently sized particles as in the following:

Case 1. Combination between P_1 and P_1 .

Energy lost = 0, since the two particles are initially at the same potential.

Case 2. Combination between P_1 and P_2 .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Energy lost} &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{(1.59C_1 q_1 - 2q_1 C_1)^2}{C_1 \times 1.59C_1 \times 2.59C_1} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{q_1^2}{C_1} \times 0.07 = 0.07 E_1. \quad \left[\because E_1 = \frac{q_1^2}{2 C_1} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Case 3. Combination between P_1 and P_3 .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Energy lost} &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{(2.07 C_1 q_1 - 3q_1 C_1)^2}{C_1 \times 2.07C_1 \times 3.07C_1} \\ &= 0.14 \times \frac{q_1^2}{2 C_1} = 0.14 E_1. \end{aligned}$$

Case 4. Combination between P_1 and P_4 .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Energy lost} &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{(2.53 C_1 q_1 - 4 q_1 C_1)^2}{C_1 \times 2.53 C_1 \times 3.53 C_1} \\ &= 0.24 \times \frac{q_1^2}{2 C_1} = 0.24 E_1. \end{aligned}$$

Case 5. Combination between P_1 and P_5 .

$$\text{Energy lost} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{(2.92 C_1 q_1 - 5q_1 C_1)^2}{C_1 \times 2.92 C_1 \times 3.92 C_1} = 0.38 E_1.$$

Case 6. Combination between P_2 and P_2 .

Energy lost = 0, since both are at the same potential.

Case 7. Combination between P_2 and P_3 .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Energy lost} &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{(2.07 C_1 \times 2 q_1 - 3 q_1 \times 1.59 C_1)^2}{1.59 C_1 \times 2.07 C_1 \times 3.66 C_1} \\ &= 0.03 \times \frac{q_1^2}{2C_1} = 0.03 E_1. \end{aligned}$$

It will appear from the above calculations that the amounts of energy lost in the cases 1—7 are in the ratio of 0 : 1 : 2 : 3.5 :

5.5 : 0 : 0.5 which shows that the more complex the particles with which a primary particle combines, the greater is the loss of energy.

If we assume with Burton (*loc. cit.*) that a colloid particle with its double layer can be considered as a charged condenser we can apply the above considerations in considering the distribution of charges with the growth of the particles. It has been shown by Rene Audubert (*Ann. Physik*, 1922, 18, 5; Alexander "Colloid Chemistry," Vol. I, p. 360) that the particles in a sulphur sol are nearly spherical in form and "the aggregation conserves the spherical form of the grains". Thus in the case of the sulphur sol studied here the distribution of the charge on the surface of the primary as well as of the complex particles remains uniform as in the case of metallic spherical condensers. Now, any unstable system when left to itself will tend towards a state with minimum energy content. In other words, it will follow that course, in which there is maximum loss of energy. If then we regard a monodisperse sol—electrolyte mixture coagulating slowly as such a system and associate the rate of coagulation with the rate of loss of energy, it is apparent from the above considerations, that during the earlier stages there will be little tendency towards coagulation since as in case 1, the combination between two single particles to give a double one entails no loss of energy. From the cases considered above it is apparent that in the case of a combination of a primary particle with a multiple particle there is a greater loss of electrical energy than in the case of combination between two primary particles. This loss increases with the increase in the complexity of the multiple particle. Thus with the advance of coagulation the probability is that the P_1 particles will combine more and more with particles of gradually increasing complexity. This conclusion is supported by the ultra-microscopic observations of Wiegner (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1916, 8, 65, and of Galecki (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1912, 74, 174) who observed that during the process of slow coagulation instead of two primary particles combining with each other, the primary particles combined preferably with multiple particles.

In slow coagulation, therefore, with partially discharged particles the rate at any stage will depend on (a) the number of primary particles, and, (b) the number of multiple particles.

The S-shaped autocatalytic nature of slow coagulation curves observed by so many different investigators, can now be easily explained. Initially (a) is high and (b) is low, whence the rate is slow

as in the lower part of the S-shaped curves. As (b) is increasing and (a) is decreasing, a time soon comes when both (a) and (b) have considerably high values. It is here that the rate is very high as in the steep portion of the S-shaped curves. After this stage is passed there is a great diminution of (a) and though (b) is high, the rate is slowed down again as in the top portion of the S-shaped curves. Thus it is the dearth of the multiple particles in the beginning and the dearth of the primary particles towards the end which are responsible for the slowness of the rate in the beginning and in the end.

Attempts have been made to verify the above conclusions by diluting the sol and by inoculating the system with coarse particles. When a sol is fairly diluted the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation process vanishes as can be seen clearly from Fig. 2 in Part I (p. 510). Desai and Patel (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 128) have also found that the coagulation of ThO_2 sol loses its autocatalytic nature on dilution. According to the considerations advanced here, the effect of dilution is to decrease the concentration of primary particles in the system. For the rate of coagulation to increase, it is necessary that the concentration of both primary and complex particles must be high. In the case of the dilute sol the concentration of primary particles is fairly low from the beginning and hence the proportion between the concentration of primary and secondary particles always remains lower than that in the case of a concentrated sol. Consequently there is no abrupt rise in the rate of the reaction and the autocatalytic nature is much less prominent than that in the case of a concentrated sol.

FIG. 1.

In a series of experiments, 0.5 c.c. of sulphur sol was mixed with 1.5 c.c. of $N/4$ -KCl and 3 c.c. of water and the rate of coagulation was followed on the Tyndallmeter. The results are plotted in curve A of Fig. 1, which is distinctly autocatalytic. The experiments were repeated with sols which were inoculated with some coarse particles. The inoculation was done by adding to a fresh sample of the sol-electrolyte mixture, a few drops of the same mixture where coagulation has been allowed to proceed for a period of 10 and 14 minutes. The results are shown in the curves B and C of Fig. 1, whence it will be seen that the autocatalytic nature becomes less pronounced in curve B and practically vanished in curve C. Thus when a sol is inoculated with sufficient coarse particles its coagulation is no longer autocatalytic. This behaviour is readily explained on the basis of the considerations advanced in the earlier parts of this paper. The inoculation of a sol with coarse particles really means an increased concentration of complex particles in the system. Thus from the very beginning there is an appreciable concentration of both primary and multiple particles. Hence the chances of adhesion are fairly large all throughout and the slow rate of coagulation usually observed in the initial stages is no longer prominent.

It has been shown in Part I (*loc. cit.*) that the deviation from Smoluchowski's equation in the slow coagulation of a monodisperse sulphur sol is such that the rate is higher than that required by the theory. On the other hand with a polydisperse As_2S_3 sol, Mukherjee and Papaconstantinou (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the rate becomes slower and slower than that required by the theory. Anderson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 19, 623) has tried to explain this slowness by assuming that the particles are initially possessed of different amounts of charges, so that as coagulation proceeds those with smaller charges are soon coagulated leaving behind the others with higher charges as a result of which the rate becomes slower and slower. This explanation, however, does not satisfy the observation on the monodisperse sulphur sol, where an increase has been obtained.

From the considerations advanced above it is clear that in a monodisperse sulphur sol coagulating slowly, the accelerating effect due to the gradual appearance of complex particles in the system will be more prominent. However, in the case of a polydisperse As_2S_3 sol this effect will be marked by the retarding effect due to the fast disappearance of the primary particles which readily combine with

the complex particles already present, so that only the latter having less tendency to combine between themselves are left behind.

In a polydisperse sol, therefore, the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation curves will be less pronounced than in a monodisperse sol. This is actually the case as has been shown by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 591) with an As_2S_3 sol, where the S-shaped curve appears only at one or two particular electrolyte concentrations, whereas with the monodisperse sulphur sol, unless very dilute, the autocatalytic nature persists over a wider range of electrolyte concentrations (*cf.* Fig. 1, Part I).

If now the deviations from Smoluchowski's equation during the later stages of slow coagulation be really due to the appearance of these complex particles, then this disturbing effect can be minimised to a great extent, if not altogether avoided, by inoculating the sol initially with some coarse particles as mentioned above. Accordingly a set of measurements were first taken without any inoculation and the results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Curve $\rightarrow$	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	Ratio values.				
Electrolyte conc. (m. mols/litre) $\rightarrow$	125	100	85	80	75	70					
Intensity (scale readings).	T (sec.)	T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4	T_5	$\frac{T_1}{T}$	$\frac{T_2}{T}$	$\frac{T_3}{T}$	$\frac{T_4}{T}$	$\frac{T_5}{T}$
88.5	9	45	192	198	480	618	5	21	22	53	68
88	12	70	222	300	570	810	5.8	18	25	47	67
87	16	92	267	402	690	1050	6	19	25	43	65
86	21	108	312	460	790	1260	5	15	21	38	60
85	27	126	350	510	870	1425	5	13	19	31	52
84	32	140	390	560	942	1620	4.5	12	17	29	51
83	36	156	420	606	1020	1710	4	11	16	28	48

From these data, a series of curves I—VI, have been obtained, whence it is seen that to reach the same stage of coalescence, say, corresponding to I value 85.5, the times taken are, 24 seconds 2, 5½, 8, 14, and 22½ minutes respectively for the different rates

of coagulations as represented in curves I—VI. If now, the above measurements are repeated, with inoculation with a fixed small quantity of the corresponding sol—electrolyte mixtures, the particles on which have been allowed to grow for the above periods, then the curves so obtained should be in a sense comparable between themselves, since the only effect of thus inoculating, is to introduce the same number of similar coarse particles every time without changing the electrolyte concentration. Thus corresponding to curve II in Fig. 2, a mixture of 2 c.c. of $N/4$ -KCl and 0.5 c.c. of sulphur sol with 2.5 c.c. of water was allowed to grow for 2 minutes at the end of which 0.5 c.c. of this semi-turbid mixture, 2 c.c. of $N/4$ -KCl, 0.5 c.c. of sulphur sol and 2.5 c.c. of water were mixed together simultaneously and the rate of coagulation was followed by the Tyndallmeter as represented in curve II (a), Fig. 3. In the same way curves I (a) to VI (a) were obtained as plotted in Fig. 3 from the data given in Table II.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

TABLE II.

Curve	→	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	Ratio values.				
Electrolyte conc. (m. mols./litre)→		125	100	85	80	75	70	$\frac{T_1}{T}$	$\frac{T_2}{T}$	$\frac{T_3}{T}$	$\frac{T_4}{T}$	$\frac{T_5}{T}$
Intensity (scale reading).		T (Sec).	T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4	T_5					
88.5		9	27	102	120	240	375	3	11	13	27	41
88		12	42	144	174	402	570	3.5	12	14	33	47
87		16	63	200	260	615	840	4	12	16	37	52
86		21	80	240	348	774	1002	4	11	16	32	49
85		27	96	278	420	897	1152	4	10	15	33	43
84		32	110	312	495	1020	1305	3.5	10	15	32	44
83		36	126	348	555	1100	1488	3.5	10	15	31	41

A comparison of the values of the constants T_1/T , T_2/T , etc., from Tables I and II at once shows that whereas in the former it is steadily decreasing, it is fairly constant in the latter, which supports the views advanced before.

The above considerations throw a greater insight into the mechanism of slow coagulation in as much as coagulation takes place more by the growth of the primary particles on the multiple particles present in the sol than by forming fresh combinations between primary particles themselves. This also satisfactorily explains a number of well known phenomena in Colloid Chemistry. Thus, the disappearance of autocatalytic nature on continued dialysis of the sol, as observed by Desai and Patel (*loc. cit.*) on ThO_2 sol can be attributed to the continued increase in the number of complex particles formed in the sol owing to the gradual removal of the peptising ions which also explains the continuous decrease in the flocculation value of KCl with the progress of dialysis of a $\text{e}(\text{OH})_3$ sol as observed by Desai and Barve (*Nature*, 1931, 128,

907).* The phenomena of "acclimatisation" and "ageing effect" may also be similarly attributed to the difference in the number of complex particles formed in the same sol under different conditions.

It thus seems reasonable to conclude that Smoluchowski's theory is of limited applicability to cases of slow coagulation, ϵ , the "adherence factor" is not a constant but a function of time, increasing with it along with the growing size of the particles.

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* The recent observation by Mehta and Joseph (*loc. cit.*) that the rate of coagulation of an imperfectly dialysed TiO_2 sol is higher, while that of the same sol with prolonged dialysis is lower than that required by Smoluchowski's theory, also receives a similar interpretation.

